

Social Media Usage In Pedagogical Activities Among Lecturers In Rivers State Polytechnics: Implication For Quality Assurance.

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Abstract

This study used a descriptive survey research approach to explore how professors at Rivers State Polytechnic used social media in instructional activities: Implications for quality assurance. Polytechnics in the state of Rivers were the focus of the investigation. In Rivers State, Nigeria, the study was conducted at Eastern Polytechnic and Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic. 56 lecturers from Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and 51 lecturers from Eastern Polytechnic made up the study's population. The study employed a sample of 100 lecturers from two polytechnics in Rivers State. For the study, stratified sampling was employed. A structured questionnaire was the method employed in this study to gather data from respondents. Using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to measure face validity, it was possible to achieve a reliability coefficient of 0.72 for the structured questionnaires. Z-test was employed to evaluate hypotheses, whereas mean and standard deviation were used to respond to research questions. According to the study, social media has the potential to be used for research and teaching; it also presents a fresh way to forge connections between students or learners and their institutions. The researcher suggested that lecturers encourage other academics to use social networking sites in their teaching and research publications in light of the findings.

Keywords: Social media, quality assurance, web-based learning, online learning, dispersed learning, computer-assisted instruction,

Introduction

Information technology can be used to make other daily tasks easier, such as ordering tickets and other forms of transportation online, communicating with others online, searching for and purchasing a variety of items, and more. As a result, technological advancements have an impact on many facets of daily life. One such example is how the use of smartphones in the classroom. In the past, instructors served as information providers, but today, that function has changed, and there is a lot of emphasis on integrating technology in the classroom through creative teaching methods that put the needs of the students first (Hwang et al, 2015).

Technology helps students become more engaged, which is essential for achieving the targeted learning objectives (Northey et al., 2015). (Bolkan, 2015). In contrast to the past, when courses were held directly (face to face), the contemporary teaching and learning process is teacher-centered, with teachers utilizing visual aids in the form of slide presentations and visualizers. Hence, teachers must be proficient in using a variety of technologies as well as designing, compiling, supervising, and grading students' projects. This new position is demanding and necessitates a different strategy for teacher professional development.

Students can utilize social media to conduct additional research for their assignments and projects because it offers pertinent and trustworthy information. Online users, students, gamers, professionals, and everyday people with shared interests can connect more effectively, more quickly, and continuously thanks to social media. Social media's special capacity to bring people back together online enables users to get in touch with former friends, neighbors, coworkers, or classmates (Bolkan, 2015).

The most popular approach to incorporating new media into the classroom is to complement the necessary skill set with the aptitude and attitude that are most strongly associated with it. The majority of primary and secondary education still takes place in classrooms. Social media frequently discusses the student's personal situation and manner of living. There aren't many social media channels that have been created to speak to the whole class of kids (Storey, Briggs

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& Russel, 2020). The daily operations of preschools, primary, special, and secondary schools, services, and local governments all include quality assurance in education. To ensure that high standards are preserved and that outcomes for children and teenagers are improved, staff members participate in a number of activities. They include planning for improvement, monitoring, and self-reflection. Because assessment is an essential part of learning, teaching, and the curriculum, these quality assurance strategies also apply to it.

Rigid and robust procedures will also be essential as part of a comprehensive general education to ensure the accuracy of information offered on progress and accomplishments, especially during times of transition (Roddy, Danielle, Chung, Christopher, Shaw, Stephen, Filia, Jason & Matthew, 2017). Markus (2019) defines e-learning as a learning process that involves interaction with digitally provided content, network-based services, and tutoring help. Personalized, flexible, individual, self-organized, collaborative learning centered on a community of students, teachers, facilitators, and specialists is replacing traditional education or training.

Any technologically mediated learning that uses computers, whether online or in a physical classroom environment (computer assisted learning), is referred to as e-learning (Zdrava, 2018). A shift toward the application of adult learning theory, where educators take on a larger role as facilitators of learning and competency evaluators rather than just information producers, may be sparked by the inclusion of e-learning into education. E-learning is the process of utilizing Internet technology to deliver a variety of solutions that enhance knowledge and performance (Akram, & Bushra, 2020). Despite the fact that utilization varies considerably amongst medical schools and has increased over the past 10 years, it appears to be more common in basic science courses than in clinical clerkships.

E-learning is also known as web-based learning, online learning, dispersed learning, computer-assisted instruction, or Internet-based learning. In the past, distance learning and computer-assisted education were the two most widely used e-learning techniques. In remote learning, information technologies are utilized to transmit instruction from a central location to students who are in distant places (Kim, & Sei-ching, 2020). Academics, administrators, and students have discovered that multimedia e-learning enhances instruction and learning. The two types of

these advantages are learning delivery and learning augmentation. Learning delivery, which includes better access to information, content standards, customized training, ease of distribution, and accountability, is the most commonly mentioned advantage of e-learning.

When something is accessible, a user can find it when they need it (Suman & Vardhan, 2014). Access to educational resources is essential because learning typically occurs on the fly. Because to e-learning technology, updating electronic content is easier and quicker than updating printed materials. Since they have control over the material, learning method, learning speed, time, and frequently the media, learners may tailor their experience to meet their own learning goals (Shabnoor & Singh, 2021). Furthermore, outcomes evaluation can be added to e-learning systems to demonstrate whether learning has occurred (Manning, 2014). For the purposes of this study, the researcher will only focus on a handful of the websites that students regularly use for educational reasons: Facebook, Twitter, Opera Mini, Skype, YouTube, Wiki, Google+, Moodle, WhatsApp, and YouTube. Use of social media and networking sites for education and learning has increased dramatically in recent years (Williams & Adesope, 2017).

Statement of the problem

It seems like all we hear about these days are failing teachers and failing schools. Business, government, and economists have joined the fray, criticizing teachers, educators, and educational institutions while frequently putting up politically motivated, wrong, or oversimplified remedies. We cannot ignore the impact of socioeconomic status, family history, place of residence, and educational resources on learning and development. Despite their best efforts, no instructor will be able to improve every student's performance to the average level because it is both statistically and practically impossible to do so. The best resources we have for overcoming challenges are good teaching and good schools, notwithstanding the unfairness of life.

At the same time, challenges for such a vision statement and planning document are brought on by misconceptions and myths about the difficulty of teaching and learning, technologies available to support online instruction, the support and compensation required for high-quality instructors, and the requirements of online students.

The COVID-19 pandemic compelled the education sector to switch from a face-to-face learning system to an online one in order to break the COVID-19 transmission chain. Lecturers and students must adjust to the new ways that knowledge is delivered through online learning as a result.

The social media tool was selected for use in education because it enables the establishment of virtual classrooms. This will facilitate the transition of the passive pupils from a typical face-to-face classroom into a setting that is more engaging and dynamic.

Aim and Objectives of the study

The aim of the study is to investigate social media usage in pedagogical activities among lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic: Implication for quality assurance. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Ascertain the perception of lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic on social media and quality of teaching and research purposes
2. Describe the types of social media used by lecturers for teaching and research in Rivers State Polytechnic.
3. Determine lecturers' usage of social media for teaching and research in Rivers State Polytechnic.

Research Question

Based on the aim and objectives of the study the following research questions were drawn;

1. What is the perception of lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic on quality of teaching and research purposes?
2. What are the types of social media used for teaching and research among lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic?

3. What is the usage of social media for teaching and research among lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic?

Hypotheses

Based on the specific objectives and research questions, the following hypotheses are raised for the study

- HO₁ There is no significant difference between Ken Saro Wiwa polytechnic and Eastern polytechnic lecturers' perception of social media on quality of teaching and research purposes
- HO₂ There is no significant difference between Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern polytechnic lecturers' preferred types of social media used for teaching and research purposes
- HO₃ There is no significant difference between Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern Polytechnic lecturers' usage of social media for teaching and research purposes

Methodology

This study used a descriptive survey research approach to explore how professors at Rivers State Polytechnic used social media in instructional activities: Implications for quality assurance. Polytechnics in the state of Rivers was the focus of the investigation. In Rivers State, Nigeria, the study was conducted at Eastern Polytechnic and Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic. 56 lecturers from Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and 51 lecturers from Eastern Polytechnic made up the study's population. The study employed a sample of 100 lecturers from two polytechnics in Rivers State. For the study, stratified sampling was employed. A structured questionnaire was the method employed in this study to gather data from respondents. Using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to measure face validity, it was possible to achieve a reliability coefficient of 0.72 for the structured questionnaires. Z-test was employed to evaluate hypotheses, whereas mean and standard deviation were used to respond to research questions.

Research Analysis

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Research Question 1: What is the perception of lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic on quality of teaching and research purposes?

Table 1: Perception of social media on quality of teaching and research

S/N	Perception of social media on quality of teaching and research	SA	A	D	SD	X	SD	No of Respondents
1	Social media has the potential of teaching and research	42	56	2	-	3.40	0.52	100
2	It offers a new way to develop relationship between the students or learners and their institutions	50	39	11	-	3.39	0.67	100
3	Growing emphasis on the students as an active partner in governance, curriculum design, quality enhancement and even in leading organizations	49	39	10	2	3.35	0.70	100
4	Helps to create trusted relationships in an increasingly digital, distributed study environment	51	30	12	7	3.25	0.92	100
5	Involving learners/students as partners in their study experiences	43	51	4	2	3.35	0.65	100
6	Social media sites like twitter, Facebook and Pinterest are helping teachers and students communicate and share knowledge and also carrying out research	38	54	7	1	3.29	0.63	100
7	Social confidence amongst	29	60	9	2	3.16	0.66	100

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	students has improved greatly with social media							
8	Social applications offer assortment of tools that learners can mix and match to best suit their individual learning styles and increase their academic success	58	23	14	5	3.34	0.89	100
9	There is creativity in teaching subjects	41	46	13	-	3.28	0.68	100
10	Social networking has helped people connect with old friends and relatives	19	66	12	5	3.03	0.72	100
	Average Mean						3.28	0.70

Table 1 revealed that lecturers accepted the entire mean as their perception of social media for teaching and research. This is because the entire item mean was above the criterion mean of 2.50. Therefore, the study found that social media has the potential of teaching and research; it offers a new way to develop relationship between the students or learners and their institutions.

Research Question 2: What are the types of social media used for teaching and research among lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic?

Table 2: Types of social media sites used for teaching and research

S/N	Preferred social media types used by teachers for teaching and research purposes	SA	A	D	SD	X	SD	No of Respondents
1.	Facebook	71	19	10	-	3.61	0.83	100

2.	Twitter	59	40	1	-	3.58	0.52	100
3.	Zoom	56	42	2	-	3.54	0.53	100
4.	YouTube	80	10	10	-	3.70	0.64	100
5.	LinkedIn	22	61	17	-	3.05	0.62	100
6.	Schoology	52	45	1	-	3.00	0.53	100
7.	Edmodo	45	30	20	5	3.15	0.90	100
8.	Telegram	68	22	7	3	3.55	0.75	100
9.	WhatsApp	64	20	16	-	3.48	0.64	100
10.	Google Classroom	38	22	7	3	3.36	0.52	100
	Average Mean					3.40	0.65	

Table 2 revealed that lecturers accepted the entire mean as their perception of social media for teaching and research. This is because the entire item mean was above the criterion mean of 2.50. Therefore, the study found that Facebook, Twitter, Zoom, YouTube, Telegram and WhatsApp were most preferred for teaching and research purposes.

Research Question 3: What is the usage of social media for teaching and research among lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic?

Table 3: Lecturers’ usage of social media for teaching and research purposes

S/N	Lecturers’ usage of social media for teaching and research purposes	SA	A	D	SD	X	SD	No of Respondents
1	How many courses do you	45	51	4	2	3.35	0.61	100

	teach							
2	Have you improved the quality of your teaching materials since the last year	37	50	13	-	3.24	0.67	100
3	I update my lessons regularly	55	38	4	3	3.45	0.71	100
4	I plan and prioritize students lesson	60	35	5	-	3.55	0.58	100
5	I introduce social media tools to my teaching/active learning in class	48	49	3	-	3.45	0.55	100
6	I write Instructional objectives for every lesson since useful material are easy to find through social networking sites	61	38	1	-	3.60	0.50	100
7	Research is made easy for me with the use of social media	49	45	6	-	3.49	0.61	100
8	I have more than 10 articles published online through the use of social media sites	45	35	20	-	3.43	0.83	100
9	I can access on-line journal to get useful materials for my teaching	53	46	1	-	3.52	0.52	100
10	I connect with other professionals all over the	30	65	3	2	3.23	0.59	100

	world through social networking sites							
	Overall Mean	3.43	0.58					

Table 3 revealed that lecturers accepted the entire mean as their perception of social media for teaching and research. This is because the entire item mean was above the criterion mean of 2.50. Therefore, the study found that teachers use social media to write instructional objectives for every lesson since useful material are easy to find through social networking sites.

Hypotheses

HO₁ There is no significant difference between Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern Polytechnic lecturers’ perception of social media on quality of teaching and research purposes

Table 1 Table of analysis to determine the significant difference for perception of lecturers of Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern Polytechnic on social media for teaching and research purposes

Group	Mean	SD	N	Df	Standard Error	Z - Cal	Z-Crit	Decision
Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic	3.36	0.74	50	98	0.31	22.38	1.96	Rejected
Eastern Polytechnic	3.56	0.72	50					

The result of the table above shows that the calculated Z-score of 22.38 is greater than the critical Z- value of 1.96. As a rule, when the calculated value is greater than the critical value, the hypothesis is rejected. This implies therefore that there is a significant difference between Ken

Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern Polytechnic lecturers’ on perception of social media for teaching and research purposes.

HO₂ There is no significant difference between Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern Polytechnic lecturers’ preferred types of social media used for teaching and research purposes

Table 2 Table of analysis to determine the significant difference between Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern Polytechnic lecturers’ preferred types of social media for teaching and research purposes

Group	Mean	SD	N	Df	Standard Deviation	Z-Cal	Z-Crit	Decision
Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic	3.69	0.58	46	98	0.46	0.74	1.96	Accepted
Eastern Polytechnic	3.35	0.68	54					

The result of the table above shows that the calculated Z-score of 0.74 is less than the critical Z-value of 1.96. As a rule, when the calculated value is less than the critical value, the hypothesis is accepted. This implies therefore that there is no significant difference Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern Polytechnic lecturers’ preferred types of social media for teaching and research purposes.

HO₃ There is no significant difference between Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern Polytechnic lecturers’ usage of social media for teaching and research purposes

Table 3 Table of analysis to determine the significant difference between Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern Polytechnic lecturers’ usage of social media for teaching and research purposes

Group	Mean	SD	N	Df	Standard	Z-Cal	Z-tab	Decision
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					Deviation					
Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic	3.44	0.68	45			98	0.13	1.15	1.96	Accepted
Eastern Polytechnic	3.29	0.66	55							

The result of the table above shows that the calculated Z-Score of 1.15 is less than the critical value of 1.96. As a rule, when the calculated value is less than the critical value, the hypothesis is accepted. This implies therefore that there is no significant difference between Ken Saro Wiwa Polytechnic and Eastern Polytechnic lecturers’ usage of social media for teaching and research purposes

Discussion of findings

Research Question 1: What is the perception of lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic on quality of teaching and research purposes?

The study found that social media has the potential of teaching and research; it offers a new way to develop relationship between the students or learners and their institutions.

The current study's findings are consistent with those of Seechaliao (2015), who discovered that most lecturers had some experience with social media in higher education courses, namely Facebook for teaching and research purposes.

The findings of the study concur with those of Harisa (2016), who discovered that some professors used Facebook, the Internet, and Twitter for both teaching and research.

Research Question 2: What are the types of social media used for teaching and research among lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic?

The study found that Facebook, Twitter, Zoom, YouTube, Telegram and WhatsApp were most preferred for teaching and research purposes.

The current study's findings are in line with those of Kuruva, Gouthami, and Vijaya (2019), who discovered that social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, blogs, YouTube, Instagram, Google Docs, LinkedIn, Myspace, and Wikis were used to test how they might encourage collaboration, knowledge construction, and thinking skills.

The findings of the study are in line with those of Waseem (2018), who discovered that professors utilize social media sites like Facebook, Twitter, Google+, YouTube, Pinterest, Instagram, Tumblr, Flickr, Reddit, snapchat, and WhatsApp among others for research and online publications.

Research Question 3: What is the usage of social media for teaching and research among lecturers in Rivers State Polytechnic?

The study found that lecturers use social media to write instructional objectives for every lesson since useful material are easy to find through social networking sites.

The findings concur with those of Jamal & Nawab (2020), who discovered that the usage of online social media for collaborative learning had a substantial impact on peer and teacher interaction as well as online knowledge sharing behavior.

The findings of the study concur with those of Antoine, Marieke, and Myrthe (2019), who concluded that school boards need to recognise and recognize the purpose of social media and incorporate it into reform plans if they want to see education rejuvenate in the direction of digital teaching.

The results of the study are in line with those of Vikash (2013), who discovered that incorporating social media into education systems helps the process of delivering curricula, extends the learning environment to the real world, and enhances teachers' online writings.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were made by the researchers:

1. Social media has the potential of teaching and research; it offers a new way to develop relationship between the students or learners and their institutions.

2. Facebook, Twitter, Zoom, YouTube, Telegram and WhatsApp were most preferred for teaching and research purposes.
3. Teachers use social media to write instructional objectives for every lesson since useful material are easy to find through social networking sites.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the researchers recommend that:

1. Lecturers should encourage other teachers to use social networking sites in their teaching and research publication.
2. Other networking sites like Schoology, Edmodo, Google Classroom, Class trees etc should be used in teaching and research purposes.
3. YouTube, Zoom, WhatsApp, Google Meet can be used during cases like pandemic and other related issues for teaching and carrying out research.

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